

Low Power Models of Dynamic Latch Comparator- A Study

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Abstract: The present paper carries a detailed review on low power models of dynamic latch comparator. Comparators are among the key components in such systems enabling operation of many modules including zero crossing detectors, data acquisition circuits, and data converters like Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs). Low power is the requisite of modern devices. Comparators can broadly be classified in two categories namely: Static and Dynamic. Earlier designs employing static comparators, suffer from high power dissipation problems due to their always-ON static nature. When compared with static comparators, positive feedback and dynamic bias are used by dynamic latch comparators, which leads to their increased speed and reduced static power usage. Hence, dynamic latch comparators are used in modern world applications. Therefore, in this paper, a detailed review on various improvements carried out for the design of low power models of dynamic latch comparator is given. Also, the performance metrics of these designs are analyzed to support this review.

Keywords: Comparator, Static Comparator, Dynamic Latch Comparator, ADC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the majority of devices in the field of communication, medical, and technology use the analog-to-digital converter (ADC) as their primary structural component. Comparators are among the key components in such systems enabling operation of many modules including zero crossing detectors, data acquisition circuits, and data converters; [1]-[3]. In ADCs, the comparator plays a crucial role on the overall performance. An accurate and fast comparator is a key element in high-resolution and high-speed data converter; [4].

A comparator compares the input with the reference voltage and generates a digital output. It produces a high output, if the input signal is greater than reference voltage and produces low output, when the input signal lesser than the reference signal; [1]-[19]. Speed and accuracy are two most important factors of a comparator. The comparator has to be capable of finding even a small difference between the input signal and reference signal. The functional schematic of a clocked comparator is shown in Fig.1.

There are two types of comparators namely, Open-loop comparators and Regenerative or latch comparators; [2]. Open

loop comparators are basically Op-amps without a feed-back whereas, regenerative or latch comparators use positive feed-back

mechanism to compare two signals. Latched comparators use a positive feedback mechanism to regenerate the analog input signal into a full-scale digital output, enabling faster output transition with less power consumption compared to linear amplifiers; [2].

Many applications use Operational Amplifier (Op-Amp) as an open-loop voltage comparator, but this method is generally not accurate and leads to slow performance. Hence the latch comparators are used, which designed with metal-oxide semiconductor field effect transistors (MOSFETs); [2].

Fig.1. Functional Schematic of a Clocked Comparator

For overall successful implementation of a data converter system, the most crucial part is the design and implementation of comparator with ensuing performance. Latch Comparators can broadly be classified in two categories namely: Static and Dynamic; [3].

Static Comparator is one which includes threshold detection based on input reference signal without any clocking mechanism. Earlier designs employing static comparators suffer from high power dissipation problems because they are static, always in ON state, also they are sluggish and less stable due to the absence of a feedback path. So, we can say that static comparators are found to be simple and quite easy to design but found no application in modern world's high-speed ADCs; [3].

Fig.4. DTDLC

DTDLCs exhibit better performance at low supply voltages. This type of comparator has two discrete stages for the input and for the regenerative latch, allowing the designer to reduce the supply voltage and optimize each stage independently for critical performance metrics such as the speed, delay, and input offset voltage; [1]. The first stage has a small tail current source to achieve low offset. The second stage (i.e. latch) has a large tail current source to provide a short delay. The presence of the second tail current source allows for faster charging and discharging of the current, further reducing the delay of the comparator. The bottom tail is used as the input stage and the upper stage is used for the latching purpose. The additional devices from the input and the regenerative stage, create a barrier between the output and input of the comparator and reduce the kickback noise. [3].

1.4 SPECIFICATIONS OF DLC

As DLCs are designed of CMOS technology, which operates on low supply voltage, requires less area, and consumes less power. Therefore, specifications of the DLC are power consumption, offset voltage, area, clock frequency, supply voltage (VDD), delay, and scaling technology used; [3]. The reduction techniques are carried out based on these parameters. But it is to be noted that on setting one or more parameters by reduction technique, rest parameters are compromised. So, the DLC designs with reduction technique are considered as per the application with the required parameters.

In this review article, a detail study of improvements carried out for low power models of DLC design is done. To support this research, performance metrics table of the discussed designs is drawn.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Section (2)

Literature Review; in Section (3) Performance Analysis; and finally, Section (4) draws Conclusion and Future Scope.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

DLCs are CMOS based design, a combined circuitry of NMOS and PMOS types. DLC is a complex circuitry combined with two stages: Pre-amplifier stage i.e., the input stage and Dynamic latch stage i.e., output stage. Changes are made in these circuits to improve the performance of the design. Here we have discussed some of the important improvements carried out for low power models of DLC.

Khorami A. et al. (2016) proposed a low power technique for Dynamic Comparators. In this technique, the pre-amplification phase is stopped when there is enough differential voltage at the output of the latch stage to avoid excess operation of the pre-amplifier, hence, reduces the power consumption. Therefore, an XOR gate is used to check whether the output differential voltage of the latch is large enough and controls the power supply for pre-amplifier. The schematic of the proposed design is shown in Fig. 4.

P. P. Gandhi et al. (2018) introduced the concept of double tail in fully differential dynamic comparator (FDDC) which is a single tail dynamic latch comparator and proposed a low-offset low-power fully differential double tail dynamic comparator (FDDTDC). FDDTDC consists of differential pair and double tail latched comparator to overcome the limitations of offset and power. The schematic of the proposed design is shown in Fig.5. The addition of two transistors, MA and MB, in the pre-amplifier converts the single tail comparator into double tail comparator with differential input. Also, on the removal of outer clock driven transistors of the latch of FDDC in the proposed FDDTDC, the power dissipation and the offset voltage reduces with moderate increase in propagation delay.

Fig.4. Khorami's XOR gate Dynamic Latch Comparator

Fig.5. Gandhi's FDDTDC

Khorami A. et al. (2018) proposed a low power high speed dynamic latch comparator as shown in Fig.6. The proposed comparator is designed with PMOS latch and PMOS preamplifier in addition to a small cross-coupled circuit are used with a special clocking pattern to adjust the preamplifier gain. The clocking pattern provides enough preamplifier gain; since PMOS transistors are used at the input of the latch, and the cross-coupled circuit is employed to keep the common mode

voltage (V_{cm}) of the preamplifier outputs at a low level. As a result, the speed of the comparator is increased and is constantly high for a wide input V_{cm} range. Deactivating the preamplifier after the optimum delay reduces the power consumption significantly.

Fig.6. Khorami's DTDLC with Clock control circuit

Rezapour A. et al. (2018) proposed a low-power high-speed Dynamic Comparator which is basically a modified version of double tail dynamic latch comparator. This structure consists of pre-amplifier (Mt1, M1 andM2), two switches (M3 andM4) at the output of preamplifier and the latch (M5-10). $clk2$ denotes the delayed signal of $clk1$, which reduces the input referred noise. The schematic of the proposed design is shown in Fig.7. In the proposed design, the pre-amplifier is directly connected to the latch without significant capacitive load. Also, the parasitic capacitors of the input transistors are not loading the latching nodes. Thus, the capacitive load of latch in the proposed structure decreases, which significantly improves the speed of regeneration. The position of output-signal (Dp and Dn) controlled switches (M3 & M4) connecting pre-amplifier to latch in the proposed comparator ensures that no static power will exist in the reset and latching phases. Therefore, the static power consumption is avoided through switches that will be controlled by output logics.

Fig.7. Rezapour's Dynamic Comparator

Varshney V. et al. (2018) proposed a power-efficient low-offset dynamic latch comparator, which is basically a modified version of double tail dynamic latch comparator (DTDLC). The schematic of the proposed design is shown in Fig.8. In the proposed design, the outputs of pre-amplifier (Fp & Fn) are directly fed to the source nodes of latch stage transistors. Making the design more robust against mismatch and process variations, and results lesser input offset voltage without penalty on power and speed. Also, the outputs of latch are controlled by clock driven transistors (M9 & M10) to further save power.

Fig.8. Varshney's DTDLC

Dubey A.K. & Nagaria R.K. (2019) proposed a low voltage double-tail dynamic comparator (DTDC) by modifying its amplifier stage using self-biasing technique for fast and power-efficient data conversion. Fig. shows the schematic of the

proposed self-biased DTDC. Self-biasing technique helps to reduce external biasing requirement to bias bulk/gate of the transistors. Thus, the self-biasing technique controls threshold voltage (V_{th}) of the transistors either for fast switching (low- V_{th}) or for low power dissipation (high- V_{th}). The combination of low- V_{th} and high- V_{th} devices in amplification stage helps to reduce the delay as well as the power dissipation. The latch stage of the proposed DTDC is designed with novel dynamic CMOS inverters to improve the regeneration speed. In the proposed design shown in Fig.9, there are five self-biased nodes in the amplification stage; these are s1, s2, dt1, Fn and Fp. The bulk of transistors, M3 and ML1, are biased by the voltage at s1 (V_{s1}), and the bulk of the M4 and ML2 are biased by the voltage at s2 (V_{s2}). The generation of biasing voltages at the nodes of Fp, Fn, dt1, s2 and s1 are carried out with the changes in CLK. This bulk-biasing makes these transistors as low-threshold (V_{th}) devices, which helps to turn on fast and improves charging speed of $C_{Fn(p)}$. Similarly, the bulk of the M1 and M2 are biased by the voltage at dt1 (V_{dt1}), makes these transistors as high- V_{th} devices and helps to turn off fast.

Fig.9. Schematic of Dubey's self-biased DTDC

Dubey A.K. et al. (2019) observed that, for designing a low-power and high-speed DTDLC, the major limitation is the large off voltage which can degrade the accuracy and performance of the design and may lead to incorrect decision. So, to reduce it, the offset control (OC) scheme should be adopted. Hence, the authors carried out the modification in OC scheme and proposed time-domain bulk-tuned OC scheme, as shown in Fig.10(a). This scheme solves the issue of leakage current through bulk-node

and implementing this, authors proposed a new OC-DTDLC design as shown in Fig.10(b).

In Fig.10(a), to control the switching operation in a DTDLC, the Offset-Control scheme signals OC and BSW are used. Switches S1-S4 are used to control the input condition provided to the DTDLC. Capacitors C1 & C2 are connected to the bulk node of input transistors pair through the switch. The outputs of the comparator, OUTP & OUTN reach to phase detector (PD) and the output of PD reach to Charge Pump (CP). Both PD and CP enables during OC phase, i.e., when OC=1. During OC=0, normal comparator operation is performed. In Fig.10(b), switches S7-S10 used to disable the latch during OC phase and switches S5-S6 used to solve the problem of leakage current through bulk-node.

Fig.10(a). Schematic of OC Scheme for DTDLC

Fig.10(b). Schematic of Dubey's OC-DTDLC

Fernandes J. M. et al. (2019) proposed a modified Double-tail Dynamic Latch Comparator (DTDLC) with reduced glitches for low frequency applications. The power is dissipated only in regeneration phase (CLK=1) and not in the reset phase (CLK=0) of the comparator which reduces the total power consumption. Therefore, in the proposed design, instead of clock driven input transistors of the pre-amplifier, the diode connected transistors

(M3 and M4) are inserted between the input transistors. This reduces the output swing from (VDD to 0) to [(VDD-VDS) to 0]. Hence reduces the dynamic power dissipation. The proposed design is shown in Fig.11.

Fig.11. Schematic of Fernandes DTDLC

Wang Y. et al. (2019) observed that, mostly dynamic comparators use a pair of cross-coupled inverters as the latching stage, which provides strong positive feedback, to accelerate the comparison and reduce the static power consumption. And the delay of the comparator is mainly determined by the total effective transconductance of the latching stage. The delay not only limits the maximum operating frequency but also extends the period of the metastable state of the latching stage; hence, it increases energy consumption. However, at the beginning of the comparison phase, the conventional latching stage has two transistors with zero gate-to-source voltage, which degrade the total effective transconductance of the latching stage.

Therefore, authors proposed a low-power high-speed DTDLC with a transconductance-enhanced latching stage, as shown in Fig.12. The proposed latching stage uses separated gate-biasing cross-coupled transistors instead of the conventional cross-coupled inverter structure. This simple proposed latching stage improves its effective total transconductance at the beginning of the comparison phase, which leads to a much faster comparison and lowers energy consumption.

Fig.12. Wang's DTDLC

Varshney V. et al. (2020) observed that when comparator enters in comparison phase from reset phase, the output nodes start from VDD or GND level and takes longer time to reach its final value (GND or VDD) in comparison phase, which dissipates more power. In successive reset phase, the complete discharging or charging of final output and intermediate output nodes to VDD or GND also consumes additional power. In order to save delay time and extra power consumption, a new reset scheme is used in the proposed comparator to hold the charge. This reset scheme is called charge shared scheme (CSS).

Thus, the proposed design is an ultra-high-speed low-power double tail dynamic comparator with charge sharing scheme (CS-DTDLC). The schematic of proposed CS-DTDLC is shown in Fig.13.

In this charge shared scheme, Pass Transistor Logic (PTL) (MCS1 & MCS2) is used between two output nodes {(MCS1 between OUTp & OUTn) and MCS2 between Dp & Dn}. The pass transistor gets ON in reset phase and charge is shared between these two nodes. As the charge is shared between output load capacitances, the voltage of output nodes will not go below the threshold voltage. Thus, the comparison of input signal can be set up faster in evaluation phase and the circuit speeds up.

Fig.13. Schematic of Varshney's CS-DTDLC

Ghasemi R. et al. (2020) proposed a low-power high-speed two-stage dynamic comparator with a new offset cancellation technique. The proposed structure benefits from an offset cancellation process at the start-up to provide a high-Resolution and an accurate decision-making operation.

The proposed structure is composed of a high-gain pre-amplifier stage (as the first-stage), an output-stage (as the second-stage), and an offset-correction stage. The output-stage of the proposed comparator is used as an incorporate block and offset detection processes, therefore leads to decreasing power consumption and area. Besides, in the proposed comparator, to improve the decision-making process and offset detection the output-stage is activated with a pre-determined delay after the pre-amplifier stage. The proposed low-offset two-stage dynamic comparator is depicted in Fig.14.

Fig.14. Ghasemi's Dynamic Comparator

Anand A. et al. (2021) observed that, for latched comparators, the major contributor to the overall power consumption is the dynamic power consumption (P), given by expression:

$$P \approx C \cdot V^2 \cdot f \quad \text{- Eqn. (1)}$$

Where, C is the total capacitance, V is the supply voltage, and f is the frequency of operation.

To reduce the dynamic power of the comparator while maintaining the speed (i.e. the frequency of operation), both supply voltage and capacitance should be reduced. However, the trend of lowering the supply voltage in power saving is not sustainable due to the difficulty in scaling the threshold voltages for advanced CMOS process technologies. To further reduce the power consumption, the total capacitance should be reduced which means moving to a more advanced process technology with smaller minimum feature size. This trend is also not sustainable as the static power rises due to leakage. To solve this problem systematically, they proposed a new DTDLC design based on the transition frequency, f_T -Doubler topology; the schematic of f_T -Doubler circuit is shown in Fig.15(a).

The transition frequency of a MOS device, f_T , is known as the unity gain cutoff frequency for the transistor in a common source configuration. It is the frequency of operation at which the transistor current gain is smaller than 1. By doubling the f_T of devices, the total equivalent capacitance of each MOS device can be halved theoretically, while consuming the same amount of power. Therefore, authors proposed a new DTDLC design which benefits from a transition frequency doubler (f_T -Doubler) topology to reduce the power consumption of the comparator while maintaining its critical performance metrics such as the speed and delay. The schematic of proposed f_T -Doubler topology of DTDLC is shown in Fig.15(b).

Fig.15(a). Schematic of f_T -Doubler circuit

Fig.15(b). Schematic of Anand's f_T -Doubler topology of DTDLC

Dhandapani V. et al (2022) proposed a 19 transistors (19T) dynamic comparator. There are a total of 19 transistors in this circuitry compared to the conventional one which has 13 transistors (13T) hence area penalty is given for lower power. The additional increase in transistors helps in the overall reduction of power by turning off the preamplifier when it is not being used while the comparison is performed. At the same time, the speed is not affected as the latch stage is almost done finishing the comparison. This is achieved using two transistors (M14 and M15) connected to the preamplifier input controlled by Ob+ & Ob- (the inversion signals of Out- & Out+, respectively). The schematic of proposed DTDLC is shown in Fig.16.

Fig.16. Schematic of Dhandapani's DTDLC

Abhinav Saxena et al. (2023) proposed an energy-efficient low-power dynamic comparator which is a modified version of double tail dynamic latch comparator (DTDLC). To improve dynamic comparator, modification is carried out in the pre-charge step and the regeneration step, the two primary steps in the operation of the dynamic comparator. The preamplifier stage is designed using NMOS transistors which enables the circuit to have faster comparison speed and lesser power consumption. And in the latch stage, a PMOS pass transistor (Mcs1) is utilized which incorporates the charge sharing concept in the regeneration step, which reduces power consumption. The schematic of proposed DTDLC is shown in Fig.17.

So, these are the important improvements carried out in the recent years in the field of Dynamic Latch Comparators.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this section, performance of the discussed designs are evaluated by drawing a table based on performance metrics like scaling technology used, clock frequency applied, supply voltage, offset voltage, and power consumed by the proposed design and the conventional design when designed with same technology of the respective proposed design. Table-1 shows the Performance Analysis.

Fig.17. Saxena's DTDLC

Table 1: Performance Analysis of discussed design

Proposed Design	Technology Used	Clock Frequency & Supply Voltage (VDD)	Offset Voltage	Power Consumed for Proposed Circuit	Power Consumed for Conventional Circuit
Khorami (2016) [6]	0.18 μ m CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.0V$	$V_{offset} = 0.98mV$	$P = 2.28mW$ (36% less)	$P = 3.54mW$
Gandhi (2018) [7]	0.18 μ m CMOS	- $VDD = \pm 0.9V$	$V_{offset} = 0.36mV$	$P = 0.265mW$ (30% less)	$P = 0.379mW$
Khorami (2018) [8]	0.18 μ m CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.1V$	$V_{offset} = 2.0mV$	$P = 0.20mW$ (58% less)	$P = 0.48mW$
Rezapour (2018) [9]	90nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 1GHz$ $VDD = 1.0V$	$V_{offset} = 5.22mV$	-	-
Varshney (2018) [10]	90nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.0V$	$V_{offset} = 1.35mV$	$P = 14.46\mu W$ (32% less)	$P = 21.36\mu W$
Dubey & Nagaria (2019) [11]	45nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 0.8V$	$V_{offset} = 3.15mV$	$P = 2.3\mu W$ (55% More)	$P = 1.48\mu W$
Dubey (2019) [12]	45nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 250MHz$ $VDD = 0.8V$	$V_{offset} = 0.91mV$	$P = 2.78\mu W$ (88% More)	$P = 1.48\mu W$
Fernandes (2019) [13]	180nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 2kHz$ $VDD = 1.8V$	-	$P = 296pW$ (1.2% less)	$P = 299.7pW$
Wang (2019) [14]	180nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.2V$	$V_{offset} = 7.0mV$	$P = 72.2\mu W$ (73.8%less)	$P = 276.6\mu W$
Varshney (2020) [15]	90nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.2V$	$V_{offset} = 2.44mV$	$P = 48.74\mu W$ (46.6% less)	$P = 91.38\mu W$
Ghasemi (2020) [16]	90nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 4GHz$ $VDD = 1.2V$	$V_{offset} = 0.52mV$	$P = 341\mu W$ (14.7% less)	$P = 400\mu W$

Anand (2021) [17]	65nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 20MHz$ $VDD = 0.6V$	-	$P = 0.391\mu W$ (13.1% less)	$P = 0.45\mu W$
Dhandapani (2022) [18]	180nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 500MHz$ $VDD = 1.8V$	$V_{offset} = 2.7mV$	$P = 210.3\mu W$ (39.1% less)	$P = 345.4\mu W$
Saxena (2023) [19]	90nm CMOS	$f_{clk} = 1GHz$ $VDD = 1.0V$	$V_{offset} = 7.3mV$	$P = 16.52\mu W$ (66.1% less)	$P = 48.74\mu W$

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Comparators are among the key components in such systems enabling operation of many modules including zero crossing detectors, data acquisition circuits, and data converters like Analog-to-Digital Convertors (ADCs). Because low power devices are the demand of this modern world and dynamic latch comparator is of such type, so we carried out a detailed overview of low power models of dynamic latch comparators in this review article. Also, performance analysis of these discussed models is given to get a clear view of their work.

Designing low power models of dynamic latch comparator without degrading other performance metrics like speed, offset voltage, area, noise, etc. is a critical challenge for future applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Sangeetha, A. Vidhyashri, M. Reena, R. B. Sudharshan, S. govindan and J. Ajayan, "An Overview Of Dynamic CMOS Comparators," *2019 5th International Conference on Advanced Computing & Communication Systems (ICACCS)*, Coimbatore, India, 2019, pp. 1001-1004, doi: 10.1109/ICACCS.2019.8728470.
- [2] Kumar, Jitender & Sehgal, Jyoti & Kumar, Manoj. (2021). Low Power Latch Comparator - A Study. 324-329. 10.1109/ICOEI51242.2021.9452810.
- [3] Ashima Gupta, Anil Singh, Alpana Agarwal, A low-power high-resolution dynamic voltage comparator with input signal dependent power down technique, *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, Volume 134, 2021, 153682, ISSN 1434-8411, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeue.2021.153682>.
- [4] A. H. Hassan, H. Mostafa, K. N. Salama and A. M. Soliman, "A Low-Power Time-Domain Comparator for IoT Applications," *2018 IEEE 61st International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, Windsor, ON, Canada, 2018, pp. 1142-1145, doi: 10.1109/MWSCAS.2018.8624101.
- [5] R. Jain, A. K. Dubey, V. Varshney and R. K. Nagaria, "Design of low-power high-speed double-tail dynamic CMOS comparator using novel latch structure," *2017 4th IEEE Uttar Pradesh Section International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Electronics (UPCON)*, Mathura, India, 2017, pp. 217-222, doi: 10.1109/UPCON.2017.8251050.
- [6] Khorami, A., & Sharifkhani, M. (2016). Low-power technique for dynamic comparators. *Electronics Letters*, 52(7), 509–511. doi:10.1049/el.2015.3805.

- [7] Gandhi, P. P., & Devashrayee, N. M. (2018). A novel low offset low power CMOS dynamic comparator. *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*, 96(1), 147–158. doi:10.1007/s10470-018-1166-9.
- [8] A. Khorami and M. Sharifkhani, "A Low-Power High-Speed Comparator for Precise Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, vol. 26, no. 10, pp. 2038-2049, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TVLSI.2018.2833037.
- [9] A. Rezapour, H. Shamsi, H. Abbasizadeh and K. -Y. Lee, "Low Power High Speed Dynamic Comparator," *2018 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, Florence, Italy, 2018, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ISCAS.2018.8351548.
- [10] V. Varshney, A. K. Dubey, A. Kumar, P. K. Pal and R. K. Nagaria, "Design of Power Efficient Low-Offset Dynamic Latch Comparator using 90nm CMOS Process," *2018 3rd International Innovative Applications of Computational Intelligence on Power, Energy and Controls with their Impact on Humanity (CIPECH)*, Ghaziabad, India, 2018, pp. 229-233, doi: 10.1109/CIPECH.2018.8724234.
- [11] Dubey, A.K., Nagaria, R.K. Low-power high-speed CMOS double tail dynamic comparator using self-biased amplification stage and novel latch stage. *Analog Integr Circ Sig Process* **101**, 307–317 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10470-019-01518-7>
- [12] A. K. Dubey, P. K. Pal, V. Varshney, A. Kumar and R. K. Nagaria, "Design and Performance of High-speed Low-Offset CMOS Double-Tail Dynamic Comparators using Offset Control scheme," *2019 9th Annual Information Technology, Electromechanical Engineering and Microelectronics Conference (IEMECON)*, Jaipur, India, 2019, pp. 49-55, doi: 10.1109/IEMECONX.2019.8876979.
- [13] J. M. Fernandes, M. K and S. Krishna K, "Design of Double-tail Dynamic Latch Comparator for Low Power Application," *2019 International Conference on Intelligent Sustainable Systems (ICISS)*, Palladam, India, 2019, pp. 166-170, doi: 10.1109/ISS1.2019.8908119.
- [14] Y. Wang, M. Yao, B. Guo, Z. Wu, W. Fan and J. J. Liou, "A Low-Power High-Speed Dynamic Comparator With a Transconductance-Enhanced Latching Stage," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 93396-93403, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2927514.
- [15] Vikrant Varshney, Rajendra Kumar Nagaria, Design and analysis of ultra high-speed low-power double tail dynamic comparator using charge sharing scheme, *AEU - International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, Volume 116, 2020, 153068, ISSN 1434-8411, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeue.2020.153068>.
- [16] R. Ghasemi and M. A. Karami, "A low-power high-speed two-stage dynamic comparator with a new offset cancellation technique in 90 nm CMOS technology," 2020 28th Iranian Conference on Electrical Engineering (ICEE), Tabriz, Iran, 2020, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICEE50131.2020.9260623.
- [17] A. Anand, Y. Qi and H. M. Lavasani, "A Low-Power Double-Tail μ T-Doubler Comparator in 65-nm CMOS," *2021 IEEE International Midwest Symposium on Circuits and Systems (MWSCAS)*, Lansing, MI, USA, 2021, pp. 853-856, doi: 10.1109/MWSCAS47672.2021.9531900.
- [18] Dhandapani *et al.*, "Performance analysis of high-speed high-precision dynamic comparator," *Indian J Pure Appl Phys*, Vol. 60, March 2022, doi: [10.56042/ijpap.v60i3.56042](https://doi.org/10.56042/ijpap.v60i3.56042)
- [19] A. Saxena, A. Yadav and S. Wairya, "Design Analysis of an Energy-Efficient Low-Power Dynamic Comparator Using NMOS Based Preamplifier," *2023 14th International Conference on Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)*, Delhi, India, 2023, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCNT56998.2023.10307939.